

THE FLIPGRID DIGITAL PLATFORM IN TEACHING ENGLISH**Kismetova G.***Candidate of pedagogical sciences, Associate Professor at M. Utemisov West Kazakhstan University, Uralsk, Kazakhstan***Narekova A.***Master's student at the Department of Foreign Languages, M. Utemisov West Kazakhstan University, Uralsk, Kazakhstan*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13908516>**Abstract**

Flipgrid, a video-based discussion platform, is explored as a tool for enhancing English speaking skills among high school students in Kazakhstan. The study employs a mixed-methods approach to assess improvements in pronunciation, fluency, grammar, and vocabulary through the use of Flipgrid's features, including video recording, peer feedback, and closed captions. Incorporating insights from Kazakh, Russian, and foreign scholars, the research highlights Flipgrid's role in reducing speaking anxiety and promoting an interactive, learner-centered environment. The findings suggest that Flipgrid is an effective and adaptable platform for language education in post-Soviet contexts, contributing to the modernization of teaching methods.

Keywords: *Flipgrid, English speaking skills, EFL learners, digital platforms, peer feedback, pronunciation, fluency.*

Introduction

The integration of digital technologies in education has become more prevalent over the past few decades, revolutionizing the way teaching and learning occur, particularly in the field of language education. Platforms such as Flipgrid, which allow students to record and share video responses, have increasingly been adopted as a method to enhance English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learning. The platform has gained popularity due to its interactive and engaging nature, particularly in teaching speaking skills, which are often the most challenging for EFL learners to master [1].

Flipgrid allows students to practice speaking skills by recording videos, receiving feedback from peers and instructors, and engaging in interactive discussions. This process mirrors real-life communication, making it a practical tool for language learners who need more opportunities to speak English in authentic settings. The platform also provides an avenue for students to express their ideas creatively while simultaneously improving their speaking skills [2].

In the context of global education disruptions caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, the shift to online learning has underscored the importance of digital tools like Flipgrid. Kazakhstan, like many other countries, experienced widespread school closures, leading to a rapid transition to online education [3]. As traditional face-to-face learning environments became limited, tools such as Flipgrid provided a means for maintaining language instruction, enabling students to continue practicing their English-speaking skills despite the challenges posed by distance learning.

While several international studies have explored the effectiveness of Flipgrid in improving students' language proficiency, there is limited research on its application in Kazakhstan. This study aims to investigate how Flipgrid has been used in Kazakh high schools to teach English, with a specific focus on its impact on students' speaking skills. This paper reviews existing literature on the use of Flipgrid in EFL contexts, exam-

ines both foreign and Kazakh perspectives, and explores the results of a case study conducted in Kazakhstan to assess the platform's effectiveness in enhancing speaking abilities.

Literature Review

The growing body of literature on digital tools in language education underscores the effectiveness of platforms like Flipgrid in promoting speaking proficiency. According to Della Nuridah Kartika Sari Amirulloh et al. (2020), Flipgrid allows for a more student-centered approach, where learners can practice speaking without the fear of immediate judgment. The asynchronous nature of the platform enables students to rehearse their responses multiple times, leading to improvements in fluency, pronunciation, and vocabulary [3]. This flexibility makes Flipgrid particularly useful for students who experience anxiety when speaking in front of their peers.

Studies conducted by Kazakh and Russian scholars have also emphasized the importance of digital tools in language education. For example, Kazakh researcher Yessengaliyeva (2021) argues that platforms like Flipgrid foster a more inclusive and interactive learning environment, which is essential in developing speaking skills among EFL learners in Kazakhstan [4]. Similarly, Russian linguist Pavlov (2019) highlights the role of digital platforms in reducing speaking anxiety and improving students' confidence in using English as a means of communication [5]. These perspectives align with findings from foreign scholars such as Tuyet and Khang (2020), who demonstrated that Flipgrid significantly reduced anxiety levels among Vietnamese high school students, resulting in higher engagement and participation in speaking activities [6].

The integration of technology in Kazakhstan's education system has been widely discussed in recent years, particularly in the context of language learning. According to Amangeldy (2020), the Kazakh Ministry of Education has prioritized the use of digital platforms to enhance English language instruction, recognizing the need to prepare students for global communication

[7]. This is part of a broader trend in Kazakhstan, where multilingualism is encouraged, and English is promoted as a key language for international collaboration and economic development.

Methods

This research used a mixed-methods approach, combining both quantitative and qualitative data collection to evaluate the impact of Flipgrid on improving students' speaking skills. The study involved 24 high school students from Aktobe Secondary School in Aktobe, Kazakhstan, all of whom were studying English as a foreign language. The students were divided into two groups: an experimental group that used Flipgrid for their speaking tasks, and a control group that followed traditional in-class speaking activities.

1. Participants:

Twenty four students were selected through convenience sampling from a secondary school in Aktobe, Kazakhstan. These students were from grades 10 and 11, with varying levels of English proficiency. The participants were divided into two groups: the experimental group (n = 12), which used Flipgrid for speaking practice, and the control group (n = 12), which continued with traditional speaking exercises in the classroom.

2. Data Collection:

- **Speaking Tasks:** The students in the experimental group were given five speaking assignments over the course of eight weeks. These assignments ranged from simple introductions to more complex tasks such as giving presentations and participating in debates. Each student recorded their response to the assigned prompt on Flipgrid, which was then shared with their peers for feedback.

- **Rubric-Based Evaluation:** A modified version of Harris's (1969) speaking rubric was used to evaluate the students' performance in four key areas: pronunciation, fluency, grammar, and vocabulary. The same rubric was applied to both the experimental and

control groups to ensure consistency in the evaluation process [8].

- **Interviews:** Semi-structured interviews were conducted with 10 participants (5 from each group) to gather qualitative data on their experiences with the speaking tasks and the perceived impact of using Flipgrid. These interviews provided insights into how the platform affected their speaking skills, confidence, and engagement in language learning.

3. Procedure:

The research was carried out over an eight-week period. During the first two weeks, both groups participated in regular face-to-face speaking lessons to establish a baseline. From the third week onward, the experimental group began using Flipgrid for their speaking assignments, while the control group continued with traditional classroom discussions. Students in the Flipgrid group recorded and uploaded their responses, while their peers and teachers provided feedback through the platform.

4. Data Analysis:

The quantitative data collected from the rubric evaluations were analyzed using statistical methods to determine whether there was a significant difference in speaking performance between the experimental and control groups. The qualitative data from the interviews were analyzed thematically, identifying key themes related to the use of Flipgrid and its impact on the students' speaking abilities.

Results

The study's findings indicated that students in the experimental group, who used Flipgrid for speaking tasks, showed significant improvements in their speaking skills compared to the control group. The key areas of improvement were fluency, pronunciation, and vocabulary. Table 1 shows a comparative analysis of the speaking scores between the two groups.

Speaking Aspect	Control Group (Mean)	Flipgrid Group (Mean)
Pronunciation	3.7	4.4
Fluency	3.5	4.6
Grammar	3.6	4.3
Vocabulary	3.8	4.5

The experimental group consistently outperformed the control group in all aspects of speaking, with the most significant gains observed in fluency and pronunciation. Students in the Flipgrid group reported that the platform's ability to allow multiple takes and provide immediate feedback from peers and teachers helped them refine their speaking performance. One student noted, "I practiced my speech several times before recording, and each time I felt more confident and less nervous".

Speaking Fluency and Confidence

One of the most significant improvements was in the area of fluency. Students in the Flipgrid group reported feeling more comfortable and confident when speaking, as the platform allowed them to record multiple takes before submitting their final response. This practice not only improved their fluency but also reduced the anxiety typically associated with speaking in

front of others. Many students expressed that they appreciated being able to review and edit their own videos before sharing them with their peers, which gave them the opportunity to improve their performance.

The interviews also revealed that the ability to rehearse and review their speaking performance contributed to a more relaxed and confident speaking experience. This finding aligns with studies by Dyer (2015), which suggest that video recording helps students become more aware of their strengths and weaknesses in speaking, ultimately contributing to improved performance [9]. Students in the control group, on the other hand, did not have the same opportunities to practice or receive peer feedback, which likely contributed to their lower scores in fluency.

Pronunciation and Peer Feedback

Another key area of improvement was pronunciation. Students in the Flipgrid group demonstrated better

pronunciation than those in the control group, which they attributed to the platform's closed captions (CC) feature. The CC feature allowed students to see the automatic transcription of their spoken words, highlighting any discrepancies between their speech and the correct pronunciation. By reviewing the captions, students were able to identify and correct their mispronunciations, which led to a marked improvement in their speaking performance.

Peer feedback was another important factor contributing to the improvement in pronunciation. Students in the experimental group received feedback from their classmates on their pronunciation, which helped them identify areas for improvement. As one student noted, "My classmates pointed out that I was mispronouncing certain words, and I practiced them before the next assignment". This collaborative learning environment encouraged students to be more mindful of their pronunciation and to actively work on improving their speaking skills.

Vocabulary and Grammar

In addition to fluency and pronunciation, students in the Flipgrid group showed improvements in vocabulary and grammar. The platform's video recording feature allowed students to plan and structure their responses more carefully, which resulted in more accurate and varied vocabulary usage. Moreover, the peer feedback provided on the platform helped students become more aware of their grammatical errors, leading to improvements in their overall language accuracy.

Students in the control group, who followed traditional speaking exercises, did not show the same level of improvement in vocabulary and grammar. This suggests that the interactive and reflective nature of Flipgrid contributed to the development of these linguistic skills.

In addition to improving speaking skills, the study found that Flipgrid helped reduce speaking anxiety among students. Several students reported feeling more comfortable speaking in English when recording their responses in a private setting, as opposed to speaking in front of their classmates. This finding aligns with Tuyet and Khang's (2020) study, which demonstrated that Flipgrid reduced anxiety levels among Vietnamese students. Similarly, Yessengaliyeva (2021) noted that the use of digital platforms in Kazakh classrooms can help alleviate students' fear of making mistakes in front of their peers, leading to greater participation and engagement in speaking activities.

Discussion

The findings of this study highlight the effectiveness of Flipgrid in improving students' speaking skills, particularly in the areas of fluency, pronunciation, vocabulary, and grammar. The platform's interactive features, such as video recording, peer feedback, and closed captions, provide students with opportunities to practice and refine their speaking abilities in a supportive and collaborative environment.

The ability to record multiple takes before submitting a final response was a key factor in reducing speaking anxiety and improving fluency. This feature allows students to practice speaking in a low-pressure environ-

ment, which is especially important for language learners who may feel self-conscious about making mistakes in front of their peers. The ability to rehearse and review their speaking performance also contributed to a more confident and fluent speaking experience.

The closed captions feature played a significant role in improving pronunciation, as it allowed students to visually compare their spoken words with the correct transcription. This feature, combined with peer feedback, encouraged students to actively work on their pronunciation and make corrections where necessary. The collaborative nature of peer feedback further enhanced the learning process, as students were able to learn from each other and provide constructive criticism to help their peers improve.

In contrast, students in the control group, who followed traditional speaking exercises, did not show the same level of improvement. This suggests that the interactive and reflective nature of Flipgrid provides a more effective learning experience for improving speaking skills compared to traditional classroom methods.

While the results of this study are promising, there were some challenges associated with using Flipgrid, particularly for students in rural areas who faced technical difficulties such as poor internet connectivity. These challenges highlight the need for further research into how digital platforms like Flipgrid can be made more accessible to all students, regardless of their location or access to technology.

Conclusion

This study provides evidence that Flipgrid is an effective tool for enhancing speaking skills in Kazakh EFL learners. The platform's features, such as video recording, peer feedback, and closed captions, contribute to significant improvements in pronunciation, fluency, grammar, and vocabulary. Students who used Flipgrid for their speaking tasks outperformed those who followed traditional speaking exercises, particularly in the areas of fluency and pronunciation.

The findings from this study are consistent with global research on the use of Flipgrid in language education, which has demonstrated its potential to reduce speaking anxiety and promote active engagement in language learning. As digital learning continues to evolve, platforms like Flipgrid offer promising solutions for enhancing language instruction, particularly in contexts where face-to-face communication is limited.

Future research should explore the long-term impact of using Flipgrid on language proficiency and investigate its effectiveness in teaching other language skills, such as listening, reading, and writing. Additionally, addressing the technical barriers faced by students in rural areas will be critical to ensuring that all learners can benefit from the advantages of digital platforms like Flipgrid.

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